

Machinery development & testing

Paddy harvester developed in Tamil Nadu, India

C. R. Shanmugham, senior research engineer, College of Agricultural Engineering, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

A paddy harvester has been developed at the Zonal Research Center of Tamil Nadu Agricultural University. The harvester is mounted on the front of a power tiller, with the tiller engine shifted to the rear for effective balancing, thereby reducing operator fatigue (see photo).

The harvester consists of a reel to bend the crop for cutting, a cutter bar to harvest the paddy, and a conveyor to windrow the cut crop for easy collection by laborers. The power from the tiller is taken from the clutch pulley to a main shaft, then fed to the different working parts (see diagram). The harvester's short turning radius (3 m) allows it to be operated even in small paddy fields. The only prerequisite is that a small plot of 4×1 m at a corner of the field must be harvested by hand to accommodate the unit before machine harvest starts.

A single person operating the machine can cover 0.7 ha/8-hour day. The shattering loss is less than 1% for all paddy varieties except for CO 37 (1.7%). When reaped manually the same varieties suffer shattering losses ranging from 0.3 to 0.5%. The cost of harvesting 1 ha with the machine, including manual collection of the crop, is US\$13.75/ha; with manual labor it is \$17.50. The savings in harvest costs with use of the machine are \$3.75/ha — or 21.5%. The cost of the unit is around \$437 excluding the cost of the power tiller, and about \$2,250 including the power tiller's cost. In fields where the machine is to be used, irrigation is generally stopped 10 to 15 days before the proposed harvest date so that the field will be dry and the machine's wheels will not skid.

The unit is operated at a speed of 1.5 to 1.6 km/hour during harvest. The

Paddy harvester attached to front of a power tiller.

Diagram of a paddy harvester.

power tiller must run in the first or low gear to operate the unit at this speed.

To move the unit from one plot to another, small earthen ramps made of

soil excavated from the field will allow the unit to easily climb over the bunds.

Design details are available from Tamil Nadu Agricultural University.

Specifications

Overall dimensions: 3.85 × 1.35 × 1.30 m

Power: 8 to 10 hp (power tiller)

Manpower required: 1 operator

Output: 0.7 ha/day

Cutter bar:

- Speed: 300 cycles/minute
- Stroke length: 8 cm
- Linear speed: 48 m/minute
- Cutting width: 90 cm
- Fingers (no.): 13
- Cutting blades (no.): 12

Conveyor:

- Speed of roller: 235 rpm
- Diameter of the roller: 6 cm
- Peripheral speed: 44.3 m/minute
- Width: 90 cm

Reel:

- Diameter: 1.05 m
- Speed: 20 rpm
- Peripheral speed: 66 m/minute
- Bats (no.): 5

Forward speed of

the tiller: 1.6 km/hour in 1st or low gear

Other details:

- Min. ht of cut above ground level: 5 cm
- Shattering loss: 50 kg/ha, or 1% of yield
- Condition of the crop and soil: Crop should be nonlodging. The soil should be dry so that the power tiller wheel will not bog or spin.

Cost of unit:

- Excluding power tiller: \$437
- Including power tiller: \$2,250.